

MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE TZP PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The aim of this paper is to present results of the microstructure investigations in the tetragonal zirconia polycrystals (TZP) - tungsten carbide system. Microscopic observations compared with phase composition investigations confirmed that the reaction between composite components occurred. They also revealed close adhering of the matrix and carbide grains with no discontinuities. Crystallographic correlations between zirconia and carbides grains was shown.

KEYWORDS: tetragonal zirconia polycrystals, tungsten carbides, particulate composites,

INTRODUCTION

Yttria stabilized tetragonal zirconia polycrystals (Y-TZP) are well known for their good mechanical properties. These are due to the tetragonal to monoclinic martensitic transformation at the crack tip advancing through the material. However, still better properties could be obtained by incorporation WC inclusions into the TZP-matrix. Our previous works [1,2] pointed out that hardness, fracture toughness, Young's modulus and, especially, wear resistance of the material can be improved. It is worth to notice that dense composite bodies (> 98 % theoretical density) were obtained by the pressureless sintering.

Thermodynamic calculations [3] show that under the potentially necessary sintering conditions reaction between ZrO₂ and WC could not result in the formation of any of the tungsten oxides. However, the reaction (1)

could proceed towards the right hand side if the CO partial pressure would be lower than indicated in the Table 1.

The samples were sintered in the carbon bed. So, the following reaction had also to be considered.

Table 1: Limiting CO partial pressure (in atms)

Temperature, °C	1400	1500	1600	1700
Reaction 1	0.95	5.20	23.8	93.0
Reaction 2	0.054	0.20	0.65	1.89

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composites processing

The 2.8 mole % of Y_2O_3 - 97.2 mole % ZrO_2 solid solution was selected as the matrix material. The starting powder was prepared by the coprecipitation - calcination technique [4]. The commercially available tungsten carbide powder (Baildon, Poland) was applied.

Homogenization of the oxide and carbide powders was performed by one hour attrition milling in ethyl alcohol using 2 mm Y-TZP balls as the grinding media. Volume of the carbide additives was 20 %. Dry powders with no lubricating additives were uniaxially pressed under 50 MPa and isostatically repressed under 350 MPa. By this procedure cylindrical samples of 23 mm diameter and 10 mm thickness were prepared. The samples were placed in a carbon bed and sintered in the argon atmosphere at temperature ranging from 1400 to 1700°C with the two hour soaking at each temperature. Sintering was performed in a furnace equipped with the tungsten heating elements.

Experimental methods

X-ray diffraction was used to establish the phase composition of the bodies sintered at different temperatures. Scanning electron microscope PHILIP XL30 equipped with an energy dispersive spectrometer LINK ISIS was used to investigate morphology of the thermally etched surfaces as well as the chemical composition of the composites. Transmission electron microscope PHILIPS CM20 equipped with energy dispersive spectrometer LINK eXL was applied to determine crystalline structure and chemical composition from both TZP grains and WC inclusions. Thin foils were prepared by ion milling of the samples using the Duo Mill GATAN 600 equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 1 and 2 show X-ray patterns of the composites sintered at the whole range of temperature. In the *as received* surfaces of the bodies (Fig. 1.), ZrC is present even at the lowest sintering temperature. W_2C appears in samples sintered at 1700°C. This fact indicates that ZrC is formed due to reaction (2). The limiting CO partial pressure for the reaction (2) at 1400°C is 0.054 atm. Under such conditions reaction (1) should also proceed at 1400°C. This is not the case, plausibly because of the kinetic effect.

Fig. 2. Shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples having thin near surface layer (~100 microns) removed. It is different from that taken from the *as received* surface (Fig. 1.). In the composite sintered at the 1400°C only ZrO_2 and WC were detected. At higher sintering temperatures phases not introduced into the starting material, ZrC and W_2C appear. They

undoubtedly result from the reaction (1). In the composite achieved at the 1700°C W₂C is the dominant carbide phase.

Fig. 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of the as received surfaces of the composites sintered at indicated temperatures. T - tetragonal zirconia phase

Fig. 2: X-ray diffraction patterns of the composites sintered at indicated temperatures. Surface layer of about 100 microns was removed by grinding and polishing

SEM micrographs of the composite microstructures are shown in Fig. 3. In the samples sintered both at 1400°C and 1600°C the boundaries between zirconia and carbide grains are distinct and well defined. The increase of the sintering temperature up to 1700°C results in the rims surrounding carbide inclusions. X-ray energy dispersion microanalysis shows that in these rims both zircon and tungsten are present.

Fig. 3: SEM micrographs of the thermally etched composite surfaces. Sintering temperatures: 1400, 1600 and 1700°C (starting from top of the figure)

TEM observations of the sample sintered at 1400°C revealed that not only WC (Fig. 4.) but also W₂C are present (Fig. 5.). The identification of the phases is based on indexing of the electron diffraction patterns. Diffraction pattern taken from the border zone between ZrO₂ and WC grains (Fig. 4.D.) indicates the existence of the following crystallographic relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} [0001] \text{ WC} & \parallel [001] \text{ t-ZrO}_2 \\ [\bar{1}010] \text{ WC} & \parallel [010] \text{ t-ZrO}_2 \end{aligned}$$

The presence of the W₂C grains in material achieved at 1400°C confirms that reaction (1) proceeds at this temperature.

Fig. 4: A. Transmission electron micrograph the TZP-WC composite sintered at 1400°C, B. selected diffraction pattern (SADP) of tetragonal zirconia phase, C. SADP of hexagonal WC, D. SADP of boundary between ZrO₂ and WC grains

Fig.5: A. Transmission electron micrograph the TZP-WC composite sintered at 1400°C, B. selected diffraction pattern (SADP) of tetragonal zirconia phase, C. SADP of orthorhombic W_2C

In the composite sintered at 1700°C W_2C is the dominating tungsten carbide phase. Fig. 6. shows the TEM micrograph in which the tetragonal (Fig. 6B.) and monoclinic (Fig. 6C.) ZrO_2 as well as W_2C (Fig. 6D.) grains coexist. The presence of martensitic transformation and modulated structure characteristic for the tetragonal phase (the state just before transformation) suggests that tetragonal to monoclinic transformation takes place during the thin section preparation. This has been confirmed by the X-ray diffractometric measurements, where no monoclinic phase was observed in the as received surfaces. Crystallographic correlation observed between tetragonal and monoclinic ZrO_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} [100] \text{ t-}ZrO_2 & \parallel [100] \text{ m-}ZrO_2 \\ [001] \text{ t-}ZrO_2 & \parallel [010] \text{ m-}ZrO_2 \end{aligned}$$

confirms Wen *et. al.* investigations of the 3Y-TZP system [5].

Fig. 6: A. Transmission electron micrograph the TZP-WC composite sintered at 1700°C, B. selected diffraction pattern (SADP) of tetragonal zirconia phase, C. SADP of monoclinic and tetragonal zirconia, D. SADP of orthorhombic W_2C .

The crystallographic correlations between tungsten carbide phases and the matrix has also been found:

$$\begin{aligned} [100] W_2C & \parallel [001] t\text{-}ZrO_2 \\ [010] W_2C & \parallel [010] t\text{-}ZrO_2 \end{aligned}$$

In all sintering temperatures applied in this work close adhering of the matrix and carbide grains with no discontinuities occurred. ZrC distinct in X-ray patterns was not identified by the electron diffraction. It is probably localized in the rims surrounding tungsten carbides grains.

CONCLUSIONS

Reaction between composite components under applied sintering condition occurred. It results in the W_2C and ZrC formation inside the material. Reaction between the zirconia matrix and the carbon bed is limited only to the near surface layer (~100 microns).

It was revealed that by means of the TEM microscopy carbide/matrix contacts were tight. No microcracks were observed. A crystallographic correlations between ZrO_2 and both WC and W_2C were observed. It indicates that under the applied sintering conditions components tend

to arrange in way that a minimum interface energy is achieved. This is substantiated by the crystallographic arranging of the composite phases.

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